

PERCEPTION OF SPEECH AGGRESSION AS A MANIFESTATION OF DOMINANCE

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Abstract

The authors investigate the phenomenon of speech aggression in the texts of various directions. In the process of the linguistic and pragmatic analysis, various forms of speech aggression are presented on the actual material, and an attempt is made to analyze their use, taking into account the factors that determine the generation and functioning of speech aggression. It is revealed that the problem of speech aggression is actual in the modern world. One of the important factors of aggression is associated with a number of nonverbal and situational aspects, as well as the degree of "maturity" of an individual. The richer the communication and life experience of a message recipient, the less often he/she perceives a received text as aggressive and less often shows retaliatory aggression as a defensive reaction. The formation of an influencing text as aggressive also depends on external circumstances and the speaker's personality. The broader and richer the management tools of a text author, the more likely he/she will prefer non-aggressive methods of influence to achieve the goals set.

Keywords: *dominance, speech aggression, perception, personal reaction, Pragmalinguistics, fictional text*

Rezumat

În articol, autorii investighează fenomenul agresiunii verbale în texte de diferit tip. Sunt prezentate diverse forme de agresiune verbală, încercându-se analiza modului de utilizare a acestora, ținându-se cont de factorii care determină generarea și funcționarea lor. Cercetarea confirmă faptul că problema agresiunii verbale este una actuală în lumea modernă. Agresiunea, în bună parte, descinde dintr-o serie de fapte nonverbale și situaționale, cum ar fi, de exemplu, „maturitatea incompletă” a individului. Cu cât este mai frecventă comunicarea și mai bogată experiența de viață a unui destinatar al mesajului, cu atât mai rar acesta percepe

un text ca unul agresiv sau da dovada de agresivitate, razbunare ca reactie defensiva. Cu cat instrumentele de management ale unui autor de text sunt mai ample si mai bogate, cu atat acesta va prefera metode de influenta neagresiva pentru a-si atinge obiectivele stabilite prin scrierea textului dat.

Cuvinte-cheie: *dominare, agresiune verbală, percepție, reacție personală, pragmatică, text fictif*

1. Introduction

The problem of speech dominance and one of its kinds – speech aggression, is acute in the modern world. A person constantly encounters aggression – in texts of blurbs, in slogans of "selling marketing", in speeches of "experts" and politicians, at home and at work. The authors of texts of various orientations seek to impose a ready-made scenario of behavior on the recipient of the message resorting to various speech means, including means of speech aggression. This study is devoted to manipulative techniques that make use of speech aggression as a particular manifestation of speech dominance for controlling the society.

Investigating the essence and content of the concept of "aggressive speech behavior" one finds out the complexity of its definition. In the scientific literature, the concept of "aggression" is interpreted ambiguously from different scientific approaches. The phenomenon of aggression, its forms, types, causes of occurrence have been studied by many foreign and Russian scholars (E. Fromm, T. Mihailova, R. Baron, A. Rean).

2. Materials and Methods

There was conducted a study of the patterns of reactions caused by aggression. The study examined various age and social groups of users on the bases of the literary portal «Литсеть» (Litset' – Literature Net). The experiment included three stages: interviewing participants about speech preferences, studying reactions to various types of the texts, observing the reactions in the recipient's natural environment. Several groups took part in the survey: schoolchildren (9-11 grades), students (1-4 courses) and users of the literary Internet portal. In addition, the study involved teaching staff who filled out questionnaires with the fixation of behavioral reactions in study groups (classes). The research methodology included a comparison of the responses of recipients with the described facts of their reactions to similar types of texts and the study of the choice of speech signals-reactions to different text types.

3. Discussion

An Internet speech is oral in form and manifests itself in a monologue or dialogue. The authors draw attention to the determined thoughtfulness of an Internet monologue or dialogue, so a verbal statement or communication on the screen is conducted with the expectation of the perception of an invisibly present TV viewer. So there is a fake for an ordinary speech. And the more

skillful the fake, the more elaborate it is. Therefore, it is convincing to say that the basis of an Internet speech is a written literary language, i.e. a well-thought-out, conscious text (Kornai, 2013), (Gaibaryan & Myasishev, 2018), (Shirina *et alii*, 2017), (Murugova *et alii*, 2019). To "fake" a direct conversation, the "complicity" of the viewer creates a special character of oral, but colloquial speech in the Internet environment. In the mass media, in particular on the Internet, speech influence is determined by a triple dependence - image, sound, speech. This allows us to consider the thesis that the Internet, first, functions as a literary language, purposefully organized, performing certain socio-cultural and propaganda tasks. Secondly, the variety of forms of speech in the Internet environment is due to the specifics of the extralinguistic situation (visual range, noises, music, pauses, intonation) in which speech functions. In this regard, regardless of whether an Internet speech reproduces a written text in an oral form, or whether it is improvised, sounding, created without relying on a written text, speech in the Internet environment is characterized by such a quality as a different degree of preparedness. In other words, in the Internet environment speech is a compromise between what is prepared in advance and how it is reproduced in a functionally conditioned communication channel.

Each element of the triad "image - sound - speech" has its own functional characteristics, their hierarchy is established in each specific case as a result of a comprehensive analysis. The functions of Internet speech are considered only in connection with the main feature of the Internet environment - audiovisual one.

It is the nature of this information channel that determines the formation of a special functional and stylistic speech sphere. At the same time, the functional characteristics of television speech can be developed further, since the relationship between extralinguistic (image, noise, sounds, music) and linguistic features looks more complex than it seems to the researcher.

The visual series can serve as a parallel or antonymic, metaphorical repetition. The recipient of the message can also enter the message as a whole perceiving informative element without verbal accompaniment. Therefore, an aggressive visual sequence in television speech can create a special visual metaphor. Audiovisual unison, the functional parallelism of the verbal and visual series, is replaced by the functional counterpoint of these series in the ideological and artistic understanding of the fact, it materializes in the image and there is no need for verbal commentary or the word of the speaker. However, in the Internet environment, one dominant cannot play the main role, on the contrary, there is a fusion, a synthesis of individual elements" (Mikheeva, 2019). Especially note that the connections of the elements of the triad "image-sound-speech" are usually not layered on top of each other, do not neutralize, do not suppress, but mutually support each other by highlighting the main idea of information.

One of the most generalized definitions of aggression as behavioral reactions was given by E.P. Ilyin: aggressive behavior is a deliberate, purposeful harmful effect in order to change the state of the subject of influence at the status, physical or psychological levels (Ilyin, 2014). Based on this conception, we can conclude that speech aggression is a process of successive speech actions, actualized by external and internal stimuli, aimed at the interaction of the sender of the speech message and the recipient and ensuring the achievement of the expected result due to the damage inflicted on the recipient.

Verbal aggression is extremely common today in various types of communication, it is an obstacle to effective international and interpersonal communication (Zheltukhina *et alii*, 2018), (Baigozhina *et alii*, 2020). In modern linguistics and psychological studies, speech aggression is understood as a variety of speech acts that have different motivations and emotional components.

Traditionally, verbal aggression is understood as rude, offensive, communication for one of the participants or verbal expression of negative emotions, feelings or intentions in an unacceptable form. In general, we can say that these are insults, threats, rude demands, rude refusals, accusations, ridicules. In a textual form, speech aggression is expressed in ironic texts filled with hyphenations and hints, insults, complaints, and denunciations. In interpersonal communication, the following types of speech aggression are distinguished:

1. *Insult*. It is a deliberate humiliation of an opponent's honor and dignity. The structural formula of an insult assumes an unambiguous indication of the opponent's personality with the addition of an emotional and evaluative epithet that contains information that discredits the addressee. The most common offensive epithets are: a) comparison of the addressee's name with obscene names; b) metaphorical transfer of the name of the animal goat to the addressee; c) accusation of violation of ethical, cultural or social norms; d) use of obscene words to the opponent.

2. *Threat*. It is a promise to harm the addressee. The structural formula of the threat implies the full name of the aggressive action of the speaker against the addressee or a hint of it. A threat is expressed in various language forms: a) a propositional sentence with a subordinate condition; b) a complex sentence, one of the parts is in the imperative mood; c) a compound sentence with a subordinate consequence; d) a statement of a future fact.

3. *Rough demand*. It is a categorical form of order. Structurally, a rough demand is framed as a motivational sentence in terms of the purpose of the statement and an exclamation sentence in terms of intonation, the semantic core of which contains the imperative form of the verb. A requirement may contain an ellipsis.

4. *Rude refusal*. It is a negative response to a request or demand expressed in a form that is offensive to the addressee. The language implementation of a rude refusal is all types of sentences containing a deliberate negative speech action against an opponent.

5. *Hostile remark*. Such a remark boils down to expressing a negative attitude towards an addressee or others. A distinctive feature of a hostile remark should be recognized as its cliched (frozen, unchangeable) language form. A type of hostile remark is a curse.

6. *Censure* is an expression of disapproval, condemnation. In a form, this is a reproach, a remark, an aggressive statement of fact.

7. *Mockery (taunt)*. It is an offensive joke that is expressed to someone's address. Mockery is based on the recipient's perception of the subtext, which he/she correlates with attacks on the person. Mockery often suggests a discrepancy between what is said and reality.

8. *Quarrel*. It is a complex speech genre of interpersonal communication, in which speech aggression is most pronounced. Structurally, a quarrel stands out as a polylogue, in which the roles of a speaker and a listener are periodically changed. If one of the participants in such a dialogue claims to have a dominant role (most often - the "accuser"), then a quarrel becomes a monologue.

Mass speech aggression manifests itself in an increase in communication participants, each of whom implements aggressive actions against opponents within the framework of a speech act. One of the characteristic manifestations of speech aggression as speech dominance is a so called hate speech. These statements directly or indirectly contribute to inciting national, religious, social or other hostility.

Sociologists and linguists distinguish various forms of hate speech:

1. Open and hidden calls for violence.
2. Open and hidden slogans calling for discrimination.
3. Creating a negative speech image of a group of people based on ethnic, age, and other characteristics.
4. Justification of historical facts of violence and discrimination.
5. Quoting xenophobic statements and texts without a comment that defines the separation of the positions of the interviewee and the journalist.

A number of researchers (Tamarkin *et alii*, 2018), (Safar, 2017), (Safar *et alii*, 2018), (Sallabank, 2018) propose to consider aggression from the standpoint of self-regulation of the subject's behavioral activity. In this case, motivated aggressive behavior, deliberately directed outside the personality, is manifested at the personal level. The speech personality has the greatest opportunities for choosing the means and methods of speech actions. Hence, the choice of aggressive or non-aggressive forms of speech behavior, as well as the correlation of the latter with generally accepted norms, is carried out at a conscious level.

At the second incentive level of aggression – individually, motivated and unmotivated manifestations of aggressive behavior of a person are combined, when, along with a conscious choice of aggressive means of behavior, there are unconscious incentive reasons, which the author of an aggressive speech cannot determine himself. The degree of manifestation of an individual level of aggression depends on the psychological type of personality, his/her mental health and his/her usual communicative behavior patterns.

The third level of aggression lies in the randomness and unconsciousness of the reactions of a speaker, who is in an affective state and does not completely control his speech. In this case, the manifestations of speech aggression are purely spontaneous and are not motivated by any external or internal motives (Flores, 2015).

The fourth type is associated with the perception by the recipient of the message of verbal information from the sender. Quite often, a seemingly neutral message is perceived through the recipient's individual emotional prism. Then it is worth saying the triggering of speech marker signals that provoke the model of "speech attack from the outside" in the recipient's mind, when the recipient perceives not so much the text that was directed to him/her but the negative analogue existing in his/her memory and communicative experience. As experimental studies show (see below), recipients who react negatively to a text that is neutral in form and content, in other circumstances or with the help of a researcher – through a deliberate analysis of the text, no longer determine it as aggressive. The spontaneity of recognizing the received text as aggressive/non-aggressive depends on the communicative, cultural experience and psychological state of the recipient (Braithwaite, 2019), (Hogan-Brun & O'Rourke, 2019).

A detailed classification of manipulative aggressive texts surrounding a person is still waiting for its compilers.

Latent forms of speech aggression prohibiting, warning or vocant content: "It is recommended... to refrain from public statements, judgments and assessments in relation to activities" – a recommendation that implies the mandatory nature of restrictions on the recipient (https://kuntsevo.mos.ru/upravs/kodeks_gosslugby.php).

It is important to study the mechanism of the manifestation of dominance in the form of aggression from the standpoint of Pragmalinguistics. In this case, open forms of manifestation of aggression are understood as a direct and unambiguous expression of the speaker's communicative intention, which harms the person or the interests of the recipient of the message, or encourages him/her to take independent actions that harm his/her interests. The forms of open aggression include any administrative texts that encourage action or inaction, contrary to the possible wishes of the recipient, insults, statements affecting the peculiarities of the worldview, behavior, appearance, etc. the recipient, the exercise of his rights to social contact, etc.

Implicit forms of manifestation of aggression should be understood as veiled manipulative actions that also damage the personality or interests of the recipient of the message, but formally neutral in expression or content (De Meulder & Murray, 2017). The variety of forms of latent speech aggression is wider than open, since the formation of an aggressive speech action can be carried out not only through figurative meanings, hints, irony, but also hyper and intertext inclusions, as well as the non-verbal context of the entire communicative situation or the personal experience of the interlocutors. In a number of cases, aggressive actions cannot be unambiguously determined by an outside observer and can only be understood by informed persons, for example, the slogan «Я «Роскомнадзор» дорог» (“I am Roskomnadzor of the roads”) that has become a “meme” (a common joke), which appeared after the court punishment for the obscene slogan on the clothes of the fined person. At the formal level, such a slogan has no signs of speech aggression, moreover, its content is incomprehensible to the uninformed at all, while the recipients of the message familiar with the situation unambiguously interpret the negative subtext of the statement.

It should be noted that all the listed forms of manipulative techniques of speech aggression are considered within the framework of Functional Pragmalinguistics, since in all cases the researcher deals with a conscious choice of speech signals aimed at achieving the desired reaction of the listening to the author.

According to the degree of influence, the forms of speech aggression have a gradation, which depends on the genre of the text, the context of the communicative situation, the intentions of the author. The scale of gradation – from the smallest to the largest ones – is determined by national, social and cultural stereotypes, as well as individual preferences. In this regard, an example of the polemic that developed on the pages of one of the Internet communities positioning themselves as "philological" is indicative (https://vk.com/ph_maiden?w=wall-46299096_115727_r115762) / Об употреблении слова «кушать»/ (trnsl. On the use of the word "eat"). There is just a limited use of the word «кушать» (kushat') that speaks of the social status of the speaker. It is a marker word. And by the way, it is not only about what children eat or what valets are serving. This is what the marginals from the semi-criminal environment say first of all – that is, for the author of the statement, a literary word has the status of a social marker and indicates that the person using it belongs to a certain social group. This means that when referring to him using this expression, he will perceive it as targeted speech aggression, which is actually reflected in the polylogue on the pages of the abovementioned community.

Determining the scope of the permissible code, when the addressed text is not perceived as aggressive, is a separate research task. Within the framework

of this article, these boundaries can be determined by the ratio with the literary norm registered in dictionaries:

- Least aggressive – speech signals of the nature of recommendations or wishes, limiting the expression of the will or actions of the recipient; non-judgmental remarks about actions, behavior, etc. of the recipient, implying changes in his actions.
- Average in the degree of manifestation of aggressiveness – speech signals with the meaning of obligation, limiting, expression of the will or actions of the recipient; neutral judgements about actions, behavior, etc. of the recipient, implying changes in his actions.
- Highly aggressive statements – speech signals with the meaning of a categorical requirement or categorical assessment, implying a restriction of the recipient of the message in something.

At the same time, it should be noted once again that determining the degree of manifestation of aggression depends on many situational and individual factors, for example, the expression «Шел бы ты отсюда» (Shol by ty otsyuda – “You’d better walk out of here”) has signs of a recommendation, but is perceived as extremely aggressive, while the previously cited fragment of the regulatory text “transportation of the substances is prohibited ... ” does not cause any negative emotions in the overwhelming majority of recipients.

The manipulation of the actions of society with the help of aggressive texts does not require a detailed description, since it is widely known. Examples of genocide of one of the peoples of Rwanda, the trigger for which was a text with an implicit aggressive meaning: "Kill cockroaches" (<https://vbulahtin.livejournal.com/1347476.html>), speeches of Goebbels and others are quite indicative. And in such cases one should take into account the Pragmalinguistics approach (Zyubina *et alii*, 2017), (Zyubina *et alii*, 2019), (Zyubina *et alii*, 2020). Of interest is the actual emergence of a perlocutionary effect in the recipient as a response to the manifestation of speech aggression against a person.

The already mentioned fourth type of reactions to aggression, when it is the recipient who determines the text addressed to him/her as aggressive, draws our attention to the close connection of the displayed reactions with the communicative experience and the internal state of the recipient of the message. Teachers are well aware of the phenomenon of children's nihilism, when any statement by a teacher or just an older person, which formally does not contain manifestations of aggression, causes a violent negative reaction of denial. Psychologists associate these reactions with the child's social development and the period of the formation of his/her personality during the period of release from guardianship by parents and society. However, studies show that a significant number of people retain this kind of reaction to one degree or another in the future, although they rarely manifest themselves as directly as in children.

The authors conducted a study of the patterns of reactions in various age groups and social groups of users of the literary portal «Литсетъ». The experiment included three stages: interviewing participants about speech preferences, studying reactions to various types of texts, observing the reactions in the recipient's natural environment.

The study was carried out among schoolchildren in grades 9-11 (86 people), students of 1-4 years of technical bachelor's degree (200 people) and users of the literary portal on the Internet «Литсетъ» (21 users). In addition, the study involved teaching staff who filled out questionnaires with the fixation of behavioral reactions in study groups (classes) – 36 representatives of the teaching staff and subject teachers.

The research methodology included a comparison of the responses of recipients with the described facts of their reactions to similar types of texts and the study of the choice of speech signals-reactions to different text types. The study carried out by the authors showed the following patterns (see Fig. 1):

Fig. 1. Diagram of manifestations of negative reactions to various types of texts in % of 100% of reactions to each category of dominant texts

4. Results

The most pronounced are negative reactions to instructive/regulatory texts among the schoolchildren. Reactions to regulatory texts include, as a manifestation of restrained discontent: "Well, okay! I will do it", as well as expressed targeted aggression, including offensive character "You wish, old baggage".

The growth of aggression against instructive texts in senior grades is also explained by the prospects of a radical change in one's own status and

"independence" from the "dictate" of the educational environment: "Bring up at home, and now I am my own figurehead"; "Every teacher imagines herself to be a human being." The opposition between oneself and a teacher, as studies show, is fixed in the minds and in the future, in some adults, it causes a protest complex of a constant desire to rise above the teacher's speech image existing in the mind (see speeches by M.N. Zadornov, E.V. Petrosyan, P. Volya, as well as the steady growth of anti-scientific and anti-pedagogical publications exposing official science and school education). In the senior years of the university, a decrease in the displayed aggression is observed with a tightening of the social framework, when, by the end of training, the stereotype of protest is replaced by the approach of personal horizons of a new social status and the transition to professional activity. Life experience acquired by the age of 23-25 performs a restraining function that reduces the manifestation of speech aggression in interaction with teachers.

However, as the comparison of the data with the results of the study of the Internet users shows, in social life, aggression again increases for any manifestations of administrative texts, even if the information contained in them is justified, and their author, according to the conditional or unconditional agreement of the social group where these texts are presented, has the right to address them to readers: «Х*ли ты админ, что я тебя слушать должен?» (Kh*li ty admin, chto ya tebya slushat' dolzhen? - F*ck, why shall I listen to you even if you are the admin).

Hence, we can conclude that a directed dominant text containing signs of limiting the personal interests of the recipient of the message causes a response to dominance, restrained solely on the basis of the experience of the recipient of the message and his/her correlation of the form and content of the dominant text with the need to limit personal aspirations for the sake of higher-order priorities for the recipient of the message.

It is interesting to compare the change in the modus of reactions and their expression of instructive texts and texts of fiction. There is a noticeable tendency for the negative reaction to decrease with the transition to a new educational and social level. An analysis of the reviews shows that schoolchildren perceive the texts of fiction as one of the synthetic genres of instructive texts: «Нудно, все время учат, чего сами не знают» ("It's boring, they learn all the time, what they themselves don't know"); «Классика бесполезна - сейчас жизнь другая, все другое, только время терять» ("The classics is useless - now life is different, everything is different, only time to waste"). The perception of the texts as purely didactic and the protest against "teaching" causes a negative reaction to the texts themselves. The acquisition of social and life experience changes the idea of the essence of fiction, its place in human life and, accordingly, the attitude towards it: «В школе не читал, а

сейчас интересно, как люди жили» (“I did not read at school, but now I wonder how people lived”); «Ну, это классно, там любовь, эмоции, отношения» (“Well, this is cool, there is love, emotions, relationships”).

5. Conclusion

The change in the perception of fictional texts is associated with the enrichment of the inner world of the reader's personality, the acquisition of life, communication and reading experience. Comparison of meaningful facts of objective reality with the read basis of classical works allows one to change his/her status character, and these works are no longer perceived as “moralizing texts”. At the same time, the reader still understands the didactic and pedagogical component of fictional texts, but does not identify them as an aggressive influence or an invasion in his/her own personality. The authors believe that the awareness of the possibility of choice in relation to the literary text: the voluntariness of reading, the possibility of personal assessment, the absence of the obligation to read, etc. – removes the factor of aggressiveness of the text in the reader's perception. Summing up, it should be noted that one of the important factors of aggression, as it turns out, is associated with a number of non-verbal and situational aspects, as well as the degree of development (“maturity”) of the personality. The richer the communicative and life experience of the recipient of the message is, the less often he/she perceives the received text as aggressive and less likely he/she is to respond with aggression as a defensive reaction. Hence, it can be noted that the formation of an influencing text as aggressive also depends on external circumstances and the speaker's personality. The wider and richer the author's management toolkit is, the sooner he/she will prefer non-aggressive methods of influence to achieve his/her goals.

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